

Speculation on Two-Level Quantum Carnot Cycle

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In a previous note (1) we argue that the entropy for a pure quantum bound state is given by $S=S_x+S_p$ where $S_x = -k \left\{ \int dx W_n(x)W_n(x) \ln(W_n W_n) + \int dp a_n(p)a_n(p) \ln(a_n a_n) \right\}$. It was shown that for any energy level pure bound state for the case of a particle in a box with an infinite potential or for an oscillator S does not depend on the parameters L (length of box) or k (spring constant) or m (mass). Thus a quantum adiabatic change of the parameter leaving the particle in the same quantum state leads to no change in entropy.

In (2) a two level quantum Carnot cycle is considered for a particle in a box with an infinite potential. Energy levels $n=0$ and $n=1$ are considered. The wavefunction is $a(1)W_1(x) + a(2)W_2(x)$. Shannon's entropy is used namely $S=-k \sum_n a_n(a_n) \ln\{a_n a_n\}$ ((1)) and an expression is found linking $a_n^* a_n$ to L and T (temperature) for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. A Carnot cycle with two isotherms and two adiabatic $dS=0$ parts is considered. No consideration is given to the internal entropy of a bound state eigenstate.

In this note we try to show how the overall entropy changes if the internal bound energy eigenfunction entropy ((1)) is considered and also show how $a_n^* a_n(T,L)$ changes. We find that $a_1^* a_1$ changes as do the overall values of Q (heat) and W (work) for the Carnot cycle, but that the efficiency does not.

Quantum Entropy for Two State System

In (1) the quantum entropy for a two state system is given by:

$$S = -k \sum_n a_n a_n \ln\{a_n a_n\} \quad \text{where } n=1,2 \quad ((1))$$

The notation $e=a_1^* a_1$ is used so $a_1^* a_1 = e$ and $a_2^* a_2 = 1-e$.

In such a case $dS = -k \ln(1/e - 1)$ in (1).

For a pure energy eigenstate we write the quantum entropy as:

$$S = S_x + S_p = -k \left\{ \int dx W_n W_n \ln\{W_n W_n\} + \int dp a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p)a(p)) \right\} \quad ((2))$$

In (1) we showed that for any energy level for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls $S=S_p+S_x$ does not depend on L . For any energy level of an oscillator S does not depend on k (spring constant) or m (mass). Thus an adiabatic change in a parameter (leaving the particle in the same energy state) does not change the entropy i.e. is isentropic.

For the two state system, we generalize the entropy ((1)) to:

$$S = -k \sum_n \int dx \int dp (a_n a_n) (W_n(x)W_n(x)) (a_n(p)a_n(p)) \ln[(a_n a_n) (W_n(x)W_n(x)) (a_n(p)a_n(p))]$$

$$= -k \sum_n a_n \ln(a_n) + a_n (S_{n,x} + S_{n,p}) \quad ((3))$$

The additional entropy for the two particle system is: $e(S_1 - S_2) + S_2$ with S_2 disappearing if one change de .

For a particle in a box $S_{n,x} + S_{n,p}$ does not depend on L , but depends on n (3).

As a result, entropy for a two level system depends on the two levels, but also on the internal entropy of each energy state we argue.

Calculation of $e = a_n \cdot a_n$ as a Function of T, L

In (1) a particle in an infinite well is considered with two levels $n=0$ and $n=1$ and the following equation is imposed to define temperature:

$$dS = dQ / T \quad ((4))$$

For the two state system, $dS = -k \ln(1/e - 1)$ in (1), but we generalize this to:

$$dS = -k \ln(1/e - 1) de + \{ -kS(1) + kS(2) \} de \quad \text{where } S(1) = S_{1,x} + S_{1,p} \text{ and } S(2) = S_{2,x} + S_{2,p} \quad ((5))$$

Both of these do not depend on L , but depend on n . We treat

$$-kS(1) + kS(2) = \text{constant } C_1 \quad ((6))$$

as the change in S is taken to be a change in the weight $a_n \cdot a_n$.

The change in heat is given in (1) as:

$$dQ = \sum_n E_n d(a_n \cdot a_n) = 3 \cdot 3.14 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \hbar^2 / (2mL^2) de \quad ((7))$$

This does not seem to have anything to do with the internal pure bound energy state. Using ((4)), ((5)), ((6)) and ((7)) one has:

$$a_1 \cdot a_1 = e(L, T) = 1 / \{ 1 + \exp(-C_1) \exp(-3 \cdot 3.14 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \hbar^2 / [2mL^2 kT]) \} \quad ((8))$$

In (1) $C_1 = 0$. Thus, the internal entropy of a pure bound state modifies the form of $e(L, T)$. This is important because it affects dQ ((7)) as well as dW i.e. change in work.

Carnot Cycle

A Carnot cycle is considered in (1) which consists of two isotherms and two adiabatic pieces. dS is 0 along the adiabatic pieces because the particle stays in the same superposition of state 1

and state 2 and $S_n = S_{n,x} + S_{n,p}$ does not depend on L i.e. the internal entropy of a pure bound state does not depend on L .

In (1) Q and W are calculated for these paths where various values of L and T are used. We write:

$$e = 1 / \{ 1 + A \exp(-by) \} \text{ where } y = 1/LL \quad ((9))$$

$$dQ = 3 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \hbar^2 / (2mLL) \, de$$

An integral of dQ may be written as:

$$Q = \int dy \, y \, A \exp(-y) / [(1 + A \exp(-y)) \cdot (1 + A \exp(-y))] \text{ to see if it depends on } A.$$

Using integration by parts on has $y / (1 + A \exp(-y)) - \int dy / (1 + A \exp(-y))$

The second integral (from (4)) is given as $y + \ln(A \exp(-y) + 1)$. Thus the factor of A does not seem to change the integration form of $\int dQ$. This result is expressed in terms of L and e . The form of e , however, is changed because of the extra A , so the numerical value of Q differs.

dW may be calculated using $dQ = dE + dW$ with $E = E_1 e + E_2(1-e)$ Here E_1 and E_2 are $n=0$ and $n=1$ energies of a particle in an infinite well i.e. go as $1/LL$. To calculate dE one must vary with respect to both e and L . The variation with respect to e cancels with the dQ term, leaving only the variation with respect to L which yields:

$$dW = 3 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \hbar^2 / (mLLL) (4-3e) dL \quad ((10))$$

To see if A affects any dW integrals one need only consider:

$$\int dL / (LLL) e = \int b \, dy \, (1 / (1 + A \exp(-cy))) \text{ where } y = 1/LL$$

Again (4) gives for this integral: $y + 1/b \ln(A \exp(-by) + 1) = y - 1/b \ln(e)$

Thus the result is again in terms of e . As a result all of the forms for Q and W integrals in (2) hold, but a new e value must be used, namely one of the form $1 / (1 + A \exp(-b/LLT))$ where A represents the change due to the internal entropies. $A=1$ for the case that one ignores internal bound state entropies.

Thus it seems that the extra factor A which does change the form of $e(L, T)$ and the overall values of Q and W , but does not affect ratios. In other words, the efficiency of the Carnot cycle remains the same.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine a quantum 2-level particle in a box with infinite potential Carnot cycle presented in (2). We argue that pure state entropies should be included in the calculation.

If the two states have probabilities $a_1 a_1 = e$ and $a_2 a_2 = 1 - e$, we find that $e = 1 / (1 + \exp(-b/LLT))$ changes to $e = 1 / (1 + A \exp(-b/LLT))$ where L is the box size and T temperature.

Here A is a factor which includes the contribution of $S_{1,x} + S_{1,p}$ and $S_{2,x} + S_{2,p}$ for the internal entropies of the two pure energy states. We find that overall Q and Work change numerically due to the presence of A , but their integrals are still expressed in terms of e and L , but with the new e including A being used. Thus, the efficiency of the Carnot cycle remains unchanged.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Quantum Thermodynamics and the Adiabatic Theorem (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
2. Abe, S and Okuyama, S. Similarity between Quantum Mechanics and thermodynamics: Entropy, Temperature and Carnot Cycle (2009 or later) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1012.5581.pdf>
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box
4. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_integrals_of_exponential_functions